

Research Software: Chances and Challenges[‡]

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Introduction

A short calculation to see if we get the desired convergence? Quickly looking at the graph of a function? Is what we just added to the paper reasonable? With modern, mathematically oriented programming languages, this is a short task. The corresponding code then looks something like in Listing 1. But what if you want to continue working on it? Or look at it a few weeks later? Maybe what we concluded from the snippet is the basis of a publication? Even a few lines of code can quickly become the foundation for deeper scientific research.

```
1 clear all; close all; clc
2
3 r=2.7;
4 K=10;
5 y0=0.5;
6
7 f=@(t,y)r*y*(1-y/K);
8 [t,y]=ode45(f,[0,20],y0);
9
10 plot(y) %plot
11 title('ODE45 result')
```

Listing 1. All clear?

At the latest, this is the point where those lines of code have to be reliable and we need:

- proper documentation to explain what is happening to others and also our ‘future self’.
- tests to ensure that the code is actually doing what we expect.
- a license to share the code.
- common standards for handling data and for interaction with other software.

All this becomes important when the short analysis of a mathematical question turns into something larger, whether planned or unplanned.

For a large part of research, especially in computational mathematics and mechanics, research software is playing an undisputed role. This does not only hold true for these domains, and not only in Germany.

Two surveys from 2014 and 2017 attest to the importance of research software for academia: In the United Kingdom, 92 percent of participants answered that they use research software, and 69 percent answered that this is essential for their research [1]. A US survey [2] found that 95 percent use research software and that it is essential for 66 percent.

So software is essential for research. Therefore, development should be seen as a pillar of science and, more importantly, as an individual research achievement. Consequently, recognition

of research software and the work that goes into it are central – a realization that is reflected in the motto ‘Better Software, Better Research’.

Definitions

But what is research software? The following definition comes from the UK Research Software Survey 2014 [3]: ‘Research software can be anything from a few lines of code written by yourself, to a professionally developed software package.’.

This was refined in [4] by an inclusive and an exclusive definition: While the first basically interprets all software as research software that is relevant to the research process in some way, the second, more strict and exclusive definition highlights the research intent. Following that definition, only software is considered research software if it was developed with the intent of being part of the research process, possibly requires specialized domain knowledge, and is itself a contribution to science and research. Additionally, this definition encompasses software that itself is the subject of research. Microsoft Excel, even though still being used readily and often for gathering and visualizing data, is therefore not research software. Python itself is also not research software, the same as operating systems (unless being the goal of research itself), even though both often play a substantial role in the research process. However, this discussion also shows that the classification of research software [5] is highly dependent on the observer. Due to this necessary delineation, we follow the more exclusive and strict definition of research software.

Even apart from such definitions, there are essential differences between more common software and research software. More pronounced:

- We typically do not know what the result of our research software will be, since we are writing it to figure this out in the first place [6].
- We do not know the forces acting on a bone under load.
- We do not know the rate at which charged particles mistreat the walls of a reactor.
- We do not know what the exact solution of our Newton scheme looks like.

In general, this is different for classical, industrial software: Often the final result is defined more clearly and is usually testable.

Less obvious, but still as important: Industrially used software is primarily written, extended, and maintained by professional software engineers, while research software is mostly written by domain researchers that typically do not have a strong education in software development. Here, the spectrum is large: from the researcher with a strong affinity for software development to the researcher without extensive prior knowledge. They all write research software, and they all rely on the results. The first group is often called Research Software Engineers (RSEs), and the second is more likely to be ‘scientists/researchers who code’ to make personal preferences clear. This differentiation, and especially the distinction from a classical computer-science-based software engineer, is crucial in communication, the manner of providing and accepting support, and finally the establishment of a community around research software and its development.

Commonalities

The term *Research Software Engineering* (also abbreviated as RSE or more recently as RSEng, but context often does not allow for confusion) was coined in the early 2010s in the context of increasing relevance of software for scientific research. While software played a crucial role in many disciplines, the fact that development and sustainable maintenance need specific competencies, which are neither fully located in computer science nor in other domain research, was only realized gradually.

In March 2012 a small group met for a ‘Collaborations Workshop’ organized at Queen’s College Oxford by the Software Sustainability Institute (SSI)¹. There, the terms ‘Research Software Engineer’ as a job description and ‘Research Software Engineering’ as the practice of people working in this

¹ software.ac.uk

field were coined. The goal was to discuss the shortage of career options for software developers in research and to get more recognition for the field.

A mere 56 persons participated in the first RSE workshop at Oxford University in 2013. After this workshop the UK RSE association was founded, while the SSI was responsible for representing the young community. In 2016 the SSI organized the first RSE conference, and in 2017 the first international meeting of RSE leaders in the United Kingdom. In 2019 the non-profit 'The Society of Research Software Engineering' (SocRSE)² was established, to give the profession and community an organization that can act as an initiator for necessary change.

² society-rse.org

All these activities inspired the foundation of further national RSE associations in the US and Germany, which were shortly followed by further groups in the Nordics, Australia, and New Zealand; see Figure 1. Likewise, for the eScience Center³ in the Netherlands, the support of research software is an essential goal, in this case even on a national level. In Germany, the national society 'de-RSE e.V.'⁴ was established in 2018. The goals of the society are diverse, and membership is open to everyone interested in the field. de-RSE organized a yearly conference and offers further opportunities for networking and exchange in the online community space.

³ esciencecenter.nl

⁴ de-rse.org

Figure 1. World map of (inter-)national RSE groups established by 2025

In addition to these national and transregional initiatives, there are also a multitude of domain-specific groups that advocate for research software in their field. A forerunner in Germany is the activity group RSE of the German computer science association (GI, 'Gesellschaft für Informatik'), which focuses on RSE from the viewpoint of computer science. This particularly concerns the issue of computer science research in the field of RSE [7], i.e., research on research software, methods for developing research software, and suitable teaching and training opportunities. The activity group works in close concert with de-RSE; the individual working groups are often mixed. However, we do not want to conceal the fact that currently the view on research software tends to diverge between computer science and other disciplines, as suggested above.

Within GAMM (Gesellschaft für angewandte Mathematik und Mechanik/International Association of Applied Mathematics and Mechanics), a group was established in 2025 that focuses on the topic of RSE together with the topic of research data management. The development of research software and dealing with research data have been crucial for many sectors within GAMM for decades. They range from simulation scripts and data accompanying a publication to extensive software libraries and petabytes of data for specific application areas. The GAMM Activity Group on Research Software Engineering and Research Data Management in Mathematics and Mechanics (GAMM RSE&RDM in short)⁵ wants to give new impetus from the perspective of computational

⁵ gamm-ag-rse-rdm.github.io

sciences, foster synergies in scientific communication between activity groups, and identify GAMM-specific infrastructure requirements and spheres of activity.

Additionally, there are advocacy groups in various institutions or as parts of larger initiatives, e.g., nfdi.software within Base4NFDI or the joint lab HiRSE⁶ within the Helmholtz Association.

Particularly, we want to highlight the already existing institutional RSE groups, e.g., at SUB Göttingen⁷, TU Braunschweig [8]⁸, the University of Jena⁹, Forschungszentrum Jülich¹⁰, or Heidelberg University [9]¹¹, to only name those with direct relation to GAMM. They each show how research software and research software engineering can be successfully established at individual institutions. Both the formation and focus of these groups can be quite different, which motivated writing a position paper of de-RSE e.V. on institutional RSE-groups [10]. Especially in view of the recommendations of the DFG (German Research Foundation), 'Umgang mit Forschungssoftware im Förderhandeln der DFG' (Dealing with research software in funding activities of DFG) [11] and the GI and de-RSE guideline template on the efficient development of research software [12], the establishment of such groups at universities and non-university research institutions gains even more relevance, both locally and nationally.

⁶ helmholtz-hirse.de

⁷ sub.uni-goettingen.de/digitale-bibliothek/service-research-software-engineering

⁸ tu-braunschweig.de/struktur/praesidium/vp-dn/digital-science-support-lab

⁹ zedif.uni-jena.de

¹⁰ fz-juelich.de/rse

¹¹ ssc.uni-heidelberg.de

Practice

Development and maintenance of research software are often consolidated under the term "research software engineering". Here, classical principles of software engineering are applied to research software. However, what research software engineering encompasses is not clearly defined and can vary between domains, groups, and contexts.

For this article we use the FAIR principles in their manifestation for research software (FAIR4RS). FAIR is the acronym for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable and originates in research data management [13]. There, these principles describe the ideal case for open research data: the data, including their metadata, should be findable, accessible, interoperable through established standards, and reusable by both humans and machines.

This should make clear that research software and research data are different elements of the research cycle: research software can produce research data, e.g., in the form of simulation output, or be used to process existing data, analyze it and allow for drawing conclusions from data. In principle, research data can exist independently of software, for instance, in the form of handwritten measurement protocols, but in the current research practice, the usage of specialized software is nearly indispensable to produce and use data in a structured and reusable form. In scholarly discussions, research data and research software are therefore considered independent and equal research results.

Consequently, the FAIR idea was applied and made concrete in the context of research software in [14]. We can use this approach and derive techniques that are important in the field of RSE, to reach this ideal state for research software and its corresponding metadata.

For this we consider the following five areas:

Documentation

Consistent and comprehensible documentation is a central requirement for the reuse and understanding of research software. It should describe which functionality the software offers, how to install and use it, and under which license it is distributed. Proper documentation does not only facilitate usage by others but also supports long-term maintenance by its original developers. For this, it is recommended to use established tools and conventions to ensure a consistent structure and readability. Thereby, documentation supports interoperability and reusability in the sense of the FAIR4RS principles.

Community

Inclusion of an active user and developer community is an integral contribution to the sustainability of research software. Transparent communication channels – like issue trackers, contributor guidelines, or mailing lists – create opportunities for feedback, contributions, and collective development. Open participation structures increase the chances that external users become active contributors. It is crucial to orient on established standards and a respectful, inclusive contact in interaction. These standards can be captured in a Code of Conduct (as examples, see NumFOCUS¹² or The Carpentries¹³). In the sense of the FAIR4RS principles, accessibility, reusability, and findability are increased by a strong community.

¹² numfocus.org/code-of-conduct

¹³ docs.carpentries.org/policies/coc/

Versioning

The replicability of scientific results requires versioning of research software. Each released version should have a unique identifier to allow for referencing and citation. Usage of version control systems like Git allows for transparent tracking of changes, which can be documented by clear commit messages or release notes. Consistent versioning does not only support findability and reusability, in the sense of FAIR4RS, but also simplifies long-term developments by the original authors and new developers. Additionally, users can foster reproducibility by denoting the release version that was used to obtain the respective results.

Automation

Automated and transparent testing procedures strengthen the trust in research software, by continuously verifying its functionality. Tests that prove the correctness and usability of the code should preferably be performed automatically, e.g., through continuous integration pipelines. These processes reduce sources of errors, support reproducibility of scientific results, and simplify development in collaborative environments, all in the sense of FAIR4RS. Here as well, it is important to use established standards instead of developing individual solutions, which are hard to transfer.

Sustainability

To make a software tool sustainable in the sense of FAIR4RS requires different aspects. In addition to the aforementioned community work, longevity needs clear guidelines on how the team interacts with the software. Many of these details can be captured in software management plans and developer documentation. In a scientific context, documentation of decision-making processes and decisions is particularly important here, for example, regarding software design or the choice of algorithms, but also the handover processes when developers change, especially in the event of funding gaps. Additionally, aspects of ‘green’ sustainability, both in automation and choice of algorithms, are gaining importance. Maintenance and refactoring are essential prerequisites for all these aspects but can only be profoundly attended with the matching training.

In these areas many core techniques of modern RSEs are found. Offers like those of GitLab or GitHub contain many of the necessary resources and instruments by default: Issue trackers, automation environments, versioning, suggestions for dealing with the community, e.g., through codes of conduct, citability through connection with services like Zenodo, and many more.

There are many more approaches for defining RSE as a field. Here, we especially want to reference the classical works of Greg Wilson on ‘Best Practices for Scientific Computing’ [15] and ‘Good Enough Practices in Scientific Computing’ [16]. A different point of view is achieved by considering the competencies needed for modern RSE. This is done in a position paper of the German RSE community, in which these competencies are analyzed in detail and in close connection to techniques from classical software engineering [17].

Awareness

Even if development, maintenance, and sustainable use of research software are gaining importance for scientific progress, the funding for this area is still fragmented and incomplete. While research software is foundational for many disciplines, financing it is often only considered indirectly, if at all.

¹⁴ [dfg.de/fsi](https://www.dfg.de/fsi)

In Germany there are a few targeted funding possibilities through the German Research Foundation (DFG). This entails specific calls for proposals explicitly aimed at RSE as well as programs for funding research software infrastructures¹⁴. Nevertheless, the systematic, permanent institutional funding is missing for now. Federal ministries like the Federal Ministry of Research, Technology, and Space (BMFTR) or the Federal Ministry of Digital Transformation and Government Modernization (BMDS) have so far not established any specific funding initiatives for research software. The former has carried out a study under the broader term of ‘Open Research Tools’, which addresses similar concerns as those of RSE [18]. At the state level there are individual initiatives, e.g., in Baden-Württemberg [19] or Lower Saxony¹⁵, where sustainable research software development is explicitly prioritized.

¹⁵ hochschuledigital-niedersachsen.de/project/lower-saxony-digital-science-support

At the European level various programs are open that partially address research software. We would like to highlight EuroHPC initiatives, which support so-called ‘lighthouse codes’. Within the EuroHPC Center of Excellences (CoEs), the development of research software also plays a crucial role. Additionally, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) offers funding opportunities that affect the development and accessibility of research software. However, these programs are not specifically tailored to RSE, but incorporate research software in an overarching digital strategy.

Apart from public funding institutions, private trusts and organizations play a role. Examples are the Klaus-Tschira Stiftung or the Eclipse Foundation, which specifically support projects in the area of research software. In a current research software funding program of the Klaus-Tschira Stiftung, funded projects are working on a curriculum for a master’s in RSE, a national software award, and the feasibility and future of a German-wide research software institute. Nevertheless, such initiatives are selective and thematically limited.

Despite existing approaches, a structural deficit can be seen: There is a shortage of sustainable, long-term financing models for research software. Especially, a stronger institutional embedding –for instance, in the form of a national RSE institution or infrastructural funding of research software– could change this and allow Germany to catch up in this area. Comparable national initiatives already exist in other countries, like the Software Sustainability Institute in the UK or the eScience Center in the Netherlands, both with relatively stable and dedicated funding. Likewise, in the US, the national labs have a long tradition of supporting research software and have also established a lively RSE community with structural financing. The examples from these countries show the importance of sustainable funding for sustainable research software and how large the impact of these initiatives can be for the international success of such software products.

A core problem in both the recognition and funding of research software as a scientific achievement lies in the concrete assessment.

While scholarly articles are checked through peer review and ideally gain an independent and accepted validation, such standardized procedures are so far missing for research software. To count research software as scientific output, the assessment has to consider both technical and scientific dimensions. How a ‘research software peer review’ should be performed is an unsolved problem, for now. As a current resort, a publication on the software can be written in relevant journals like JOSS (Journal of Open Source Software), JORS (Journal of Open Research Software), or ACM TOMS (Transactions on Mathematical Software). Here, both the software and an article describing the software undergo review, and both are published together. In the classical publication process scholarly journals are moving towards reevaluation of the underlying software contributions. As examples, SISC (SIAM Journal on Scientific Computing) is establishing a section that also entails software publications, and the comparatively new Springer-Nature CSAE (Computational Science

and Engineering) journal has a code review board, which performs a dedicated quality assessment of the software underlying a particular publication, in addition to the editorial board. Other journals limit themselves to reproducibility badges that indicate both the availability of codes related to the numerical experiments as well as different levels of reproducibility of the results. Additionally, the NFDI consortium for Mathematics (MaRDI) has developed a questionnaire for software assessment [20] using the example of computer algebra and tested it within the context of multiple symposia and conferences.

Another hurdle apart from assessment is counting. What counts as research software, and what is countable as output? Are version 1.1 and version 1.2 of a software two entries? The answer heavily depends on how the respective software is developed: from semantic versioning, over date-based releases, and so-called nightly builds, towards no versioning at all, each variant has benefits and drawbacks, but all should be encompassed by a consistent counting scheme.

For this reason, a concept of a quality indicator is developed within the Helmholtz Association to systematically assess research data and software publications [21]. The goal is to allow for an assessment of both classical quantitative metrics (e.g., publication and citation counts) as well as qualitative aspects like documentation, reproducibility, or incorporation within research.

The core idea of the approach is the combination of the FAIR principles with a technology readiness model. Such a model describes levels for specific quality metrics: from 'not available', over 'essential' up to 'fully established and optimized'. For research software, such attributes can be having a persistent identifier, structured versioning, extensive metadata, clear licensing, interoperability with standards, test- and reproducibility mechanisms, or sustainable maintenance. Each of these aspects is ranked on a scale (e.g., 0-4).

The resulting maturity levels can be aggregated by dimension and visualized (e.g., in radar plots; see Figure 2 on the next page). This results in a differentiated image of the strengths and weaknesses of a data or software publication, which allows for institutional governance, funding decisions, and quality assurance. Based on this, a sort of minimal polygon can be defined to decide if the quality of a software is sufficient to formally count as a publication. Current challenges are in the interdisciplinary comparability, determination of suitable weights for the minimal polygon as well as the practical implementation, since some criteria can be automated (e.g., having a license) while others require a qualitative examination (e.g., clearness of the documentation). Additionally, this approach does not yet answer the question on dealing with different versions or releases, but is a first step towards a flexible, participative instrument to improve visibility and reusability of research software that also contributes to recognition of this type of publication.

Recognition of research software as a countable scientific output requires a cultural change within the academic system. This includes suitable peer-review procedures, establishing clear standards for software citation, and the embedding of software in research assessment systems. The goal is to make the effort and expertise needed for developing and maintaining research software visible and acknowledge it as equal to other forms of scientific output.

Part of this change is that people focusing on research software development are able to contribute long-term to science. One route towards this goal is via the aforementioned infrastructure units. They support 'researchers who code', e.g., by helping with common tasks to allow researchers more time for their main research questions. Additionally, they offer career paths for RSEs and contribute to the sustainability of software tools developed at their institutions, because dedicated personnel for maintenance and refactoring exist. The combination of domain knowledge and software competencies turns these skilled employees into valuable project partners instead of mere service providers, as flagship projects in the existing institutional RSE groups already show today.

Figure 2. Netzdiagramm (radar plot) zur Darstellung der Bewertung von Forschungssoftware, aus [22]

Conclusion

Research software has already transformed into an indispensable part of scientific practice. Many do not only see it as a means to an end, but as individual scientific output, that enables the generation, analysis, and interpretation of research data in the first place. Its nature lies in the fact that it usually is not developed by professional software engineers but rather by domain experts, which poses specific challenges for quality, sustainability, and recognition. For this reason the field of research software engineering was established, which transfers principles from software engineering into the research context and incorporates unique methodological, organizational, and cultural requirements.

The national RSE community, supported by domain-specific and local initiatives, has contributed towards making research software more visible, formulating standards for its development, and creating structures for its sustainable usage in the last years. There are many opportunities to help shape the movement, for example, through the open de-RSE Matrix chat¹⁶, at yearly de-RSE events¹⁷, or within the activity group on RSE & RDM¹⁸. Central guidelines like the FAIR4RS principles offer guidance on how your own research software can be made findable, accessible, interoperable, and reproducible.

Still, the question of long-term financing and institutional embedding is open. Without stable mechanisms for funding and acknowledgment of research software as valuable and countable scientific output, a central foundation of modern research is in danger of being undervalued. The German research landscape still has a long way to go, but is certainly not inactive, with several interesting projects and cooperation opportunities.

Further establishment of research software as an equal part in the scientific endeavor requires rethinking of research assessment and concise standards for quality assurance and citations, as well as sustainable financing structures. Only if these elements combine can the motto 'Better Software, Better Research' be fulfilled completely – with the goal of not only making scientific insight more efficient but also more transparent, reproducible, and future-proof.

¹⁶ de-rse.org/en/matrix

¹⁷ de-rse.org/en/events

¹⁸ gamm-ag-rse-rdm.github.io

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